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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Doxorubicin Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of a strategy based on the development of Zinc oxide Nanoparticles as an innovative formulation of Doxorubicin with improved therapeutic efficacy. Doxorubicin Zinc oxide Nanoparticles were prepared by sol to gel method. The solubility of drug in different solid lipids was measured. FTIR studies indicated no interaction between drug and Zinc nitrate. Zinc oxide nanoparticles were characterized for particle size, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency and surface morphology. In vitro drug release studies were performed in phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 using dialysis bag diffusion technique. The F6 batch had shown maximum entrapment up to 79.68 % and sustained drug release for 8 h. The scanning electron microscopy and zeta potential study showed formation of good zinc oxide nanoparticles dispersion. In vitro release profiles were biphasic in nature and followed Higuchi model of release kinetics. The stability study showed successful formation of stable Zinc Oxide nanoparticles.

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is the study of the controlling the matter on an atom and molecular scale. Generally nanotechnology deals with structures sized between 1-100 nanometres in at least one dimension, and involve modifying or developing materials within that size.¹ It makes the material

lighter, stronger, faster, smaller and more durable. Zinc Oxide is considered to be a bio-compatible and environment friendly material. Zinc Oxide have been used as an antibacterial agent.² Zinc Oxide can be contemplated as the most dynamic due to its great variety of applications, of all the different materials that have been studied and

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investigated as Nano sensors. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are nanoparticles of zinc oxide (Zinc Oxide) that have diameters less than 100 nanometers.³ They have a large surface area relative to their size and high catalytic activity. The exact physical and chemical properties of zinc oxide nanoparticles depend on the different ways they are synthesized. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are used in an increasing number of industrial products such as rubber, paint, coating, and cosmetics.⁴ They have become one of the most popular metal oxide nanoparticles in biological applications due to their excellent biocompatibility, economic. Doxorubicin (DOX) was initially isolated from *Streptomyces peucetius*. DOX is a highly effective chemotherapeutic drug used to treat cancers and malignant haematological diseases. DOX inhibits DNA topoisomerase II activity, causing double-stranded DNA breaks (DSB). Due to its cardiotoxicity, however, DOX's clinical usage has been severely limited.⁵

MATERIALS

Doxorubicin was obtained from Alkem Pvt Mumbai, Ethyl cellulose and eudragit procured from SD fine chemicals Mumbai. Other chemicals and the reagents used were of analytical grade.

METHODOLOGY

Compatibility Study (IR Spectroscopy)

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is an important technique that provides an easy way to identify the presence of certain functional groups in an organic molecule. Functional groups have vibration frequencies that are characteristic of that functional group. These vibration frequencies fall with the infrared (IR) frequency range. As such, passing an IR signal through the organic compound causes the functional groups to vibrate at specific frequencies. In other words, an infrared signal that passes through an organic compound will be absorbed at these characteristic

frequencies, which can be transformed into a unique spectrum.⁶

Formulation Development

Sol-to-Gel Method⁷

Two beakers containing 50ml of deionized water in each of them. Let's mark these beakers as 1 and 2. In the next step, we will add zinc nitrate with polymers (Ethyl cellulose and Eudragit) in beaker 1 and will place a magnetic pellet within the solution and the beaker 1 is then placed on the magnetic stirrer. Solution 1 in beaker 1 is thus stirred for around 5 minutes. Similarly, we will add sodium hydroxide and Doxorubicin (drug) to beaker 2 with a magnetic pellet in it and will place it on the magnetic stirrer. Solution 2 is also stirred for around 5 minutes. The solution placed in the beaker gets stirred fast due to the rotating magnetic field generated. Solution 2 consisting of sodium hydroxide is then added to solution 1 consisting of zinc nitrate hexahydrate. While adding solution 2 into solution 1, we should add it dropwise using a syringe that allowing the solutions to mix properly and hence initiate the mechanism or reaction. Also, the entire process of stirring takes place at normal room temperature. On adding the solution 2 dropwise using a syringe, we will be able to see a slight difference in the color of the mixture. The mixture will be turning into white color slowly as we add the solution 2 dropwise. This transition of the solution from transparent to opaque shows the initiation of the chemical reaction. Thus, after the complete addition of solution 2 into solution 1 we can notice that the mixture appears cloudy. Thus, the resultant solution 3 is stirred for another 2 hours on the magnetic stirrer. After stirring it for 2 hours the solution 3 is transferred into the centrifuge tube. Solution 3 thus undergoes a process called centrifugation where the precipitate is removed or filtered out and we obtain the gel at the end of the process. Around 3 rounds of centrifugation are done. After the first round, the centrifuge tubes are filled with deionized water up

to the marking and then are placed in the centrifuge machine again. After doing two rounds of centrifugation using deionized water, we will now use ethanol and centrifuge it. Finally, we will obtain the gel as the residue. Here also the entire process of centrifugation takes place at the normal room temperature i.e. 28 °C. The gel obtained as the residue of the centrifugation process is then spinned by keeping on a spinner. This is done to displace the gel stuck at the bottom of the centrifuge tube. Also while doing this a small amount of ethanol is added. Thus, the gel is then finally taken into a Petri dish and is broken using a spatula. The Petri dish containing the gel is then covered using an aluminium foil and tiny

perforations are made over this aluminium foil covering the Petri dish. The Petri dish containing the gel is placed overnight to dry. Once dried the Petri dish is placed in a hot air oven for 10 minutes and is then placed in the muffle furnace at a temperature of 500°C for 3 hours. This process of heating is called calcination. After undergoing calcination the particles on the Petri dish are transferred to a mortar and are finely grinded into a powder form. The finally obtained powdered particles are then transferred into tubes and stored. To determine if the synthesized material is Zinc Oxide nanoparticles we will have to use various characterization methods.

Table-1: Formulation Development

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Doxorubicin	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Zinc Nitrate	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Ethyl Cellulose	50	100	150	200	-	-	-	-
Eudragit	-	-	-	-	50	100	150	200
Sodium Hydroxide	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Water	q.s							

Evaluation of Doxorubicin loaded Zinc Oxide nanoparticles:

Particle Size:

All the prepared batches of Zinc Oxide nanoparticles were viewed under microscope to study their size. Size of Nano particles from each batch was measured at different location on slide by taking a small drop of nanoparticle dispersion on it and average size of Zinc Oxide nanoparticles were determined.¹⁰

SEM Analysis:

The morphology of NPs was studied by a scanning electron microscope. For this purpose, the sample was lyophilized and placed on aluminium stubs and the surface was coated with a layer of gold particles using a sputter coater. The shape of the NPs was determined by scanning electron

microscopy (SEM) (XL30, Philips, the Netherlands) at 15 kV and 750 mA.¹¹

Zeta Potential

The zeta potential of a particle represents the overall charge of the particle and stability of the formulation. Zeta potential measurement was carried out using Zeta sizer Nano-ZS90, Malvern Instrument Ltd., UK by differential light scattering (DLS) technique. Nanoparticle samples redispersed in Milli-Q water. All measurements were carried out in triplicates at 25 °C.¹²

Drug Encapsulation Efficiency:

Lyophilized Zinc Oxide nanoparticles 50mg were dissolved in 100ml of phosphate buffer and the drug amount was determined by UV analysis. The encapsulation efficiency was determined as the mass ratio of entrapped Doxorubicin in Zinc Oxide

nanoparticles to the theoretical amount of the drug used in the preparation. The entrapment of the Doxorubicin Zinc Oxide nanoparticles was expressed as loading capacity.¹³

$$\text{Entrapment Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Amount entrapped}}{\text{Total drug loaded}} \times 100$$

In-Vitro Drug Release Studies:

The release studies were carried out by Franz diffusion cell. It containing 10 ml Phosphate buffer. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (100 ml) was placed in a 10 ml of beaker. The beaker was assembled on a magnetic stirrer and the medium was equilibrated at 37±5°C. Dialysis membrane was taken and one end of the membrane was sealed. After separation of non-entrapped Doxorubicin dispersion was filled in the dialysis membrane and other end was closed. The dialysis membrane containing the sample was suspended in the medium. 1ml of aliquots were withdrawn at specific intervals, filtered after withdrawal and the apparatus was immediately replenished with same quantity of fresh buffer medium.¹⁴

Percentage of drug release was determined using the following formula.

$$\text{Percentage drug release} = \frac{D_a}{D_t} \times 100$$

Where, D_t = Total amount of the drug

D_a = The amount of drug released

Drug Release Kinetics:¹⁵

The models used were zero order (equation 1) First order (equation 2) and Higuchi model (equation 3) and Korsmeyer Peppas model (equation 4).

I) Zero Order Kinetics:

$$R = K_0 t \quad \text{-- (1)}$$

R=cumulative percent drug

K_0 =zero order rate constant

ii) First Order Kinetics

$$\log C = \log C_0 - K_1 t / 2.303 \quad \text{-- (2)}$$

Where C = cumulative percent drug

K_1 = first order rate constant

iii) Higuchi Model

$$R = K_H t^{0.5} \quad \text{-- (3)}$$

Where R = cumulative percent drug

K_H = Higuchi model rate constant

iv) Korsmeyer Peppas Model:

$$M_t / M_\infty = K_k t^n$$

$$\log M_t / M_\infty = \log K_k + n \log t \quad \text{-- (4)}$$

Where K_k = Korsmeyer Peppas rate constant

' M_t / M_∞ ' is the fractional drug, n = diffusional exponent, which characterizes the mechanism of drug. The obtained regression co-efficient (which neared 0.999) was used to understand the pattern of the drug from the Zinc Oxide nanoparticles.

Stability Studies:¹⁶

Selected Formulation was subjected to stability studies as per ICH guidelines. Following conditions were used for Stability Testing.

1. 25°C/60% RH analysed every month for period of three months.
2. 30°C/75% RH analysed every month for period of three months.
3. 40°C/75% RH analysed every month for period of three months.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies (FT-IR)

The compatibility between the drug and the selected lipid and other excipients was evaluated using FTIR peak matching method. There was no appearance or disappearance of peaks in the drug-lipid mixture, which confirmed the absence of any chemical interaction between the drug, lipid and other chemicals.

Fig-1: FTIR Studies of Doxorubicin

Fig-2: FTIR Studies of Optimized Formulation

Scanning Electron Microscopy:

The surface characteristic of prepared crystal was studied by SEM (ZEISS Electron Microscope, EVO MA 15). Powder samples was mounted onto aluminum stub using double sided adhesive tape

and sputter coated with a thin layer of gold at 10 Torr vacuum before examination. The specimens were scanned with an electron beam of acceleration potential of 20 kV and the images were collected as secondary electron mode.

Fig-3: SEM Analysis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

Determination of Zeta Potential:

Zeta potential is a measure of charge present on the vesicle surface. It was determined by using phase analysis light scattering with Malvern zetasizer at field strength of 20V/cm in distilled water and

based on electrophoretic mobility of charged particles present in the nano carrier system. Charged particles were attracted to the electrode with the opposite charge when an electric field is applied.

Fig-4: Zeta Potential of Optimized Formulation

The addition of membrane additives affects zeta potential value depending on the type of membrane additives. Zeta potential of optimized Doxorubicin Zinc Oxide nanoparticles formulation was measured and found to 35- mv.

The obtained result of the zeta potential of the prepared formulation indicates particles in the formulation remains suspended and so were found to be stable.

Particle Size

Fig-5: Particle Size of Optimized Formulations

The surfaces of the Zinc Oxide nanoparticles were smooth.

Characterization of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles of Doxorubicin

Table-2: Evaluation Studies of Particle Size Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

F. No.	Particle Size (nm)	Entrapment Efficiency (%)	Zeta Potential (mV)
F1	101	75.96	-28
F2	99	78.93	-30
F3	132	68.92	-40
F4	125	75.96	-38

F5	103	69.34	-42
F6	106	72.25	-36
F7	120	76.35	-43
F8	108	79.68	-35

Entrapment Efficiency

The drug entrapment efficiency of all 8 formulations was evaluated. From the F8 formulation showed maximum drug entrapment efficiency 79.68 % compared to other formulations. The zeta potential or the change on the surface of colloidal particles in Doxorubicin Zinc Oxide nanoparticles was measured by

electrophoretic light scattering mode using Zetasizer nano ZS. The particle charge of Doxorubicin Zinc Oxide nanoparticles were quantified at 25° C. The samples were diluted approximately with the deionized water for the measurements of particle size.

In Vitro Drug Release Studies

Table-3: In Vitro Drug Release Studies of all Formulations

Time (hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	14.56	13.69	15.10	16.10	17.12	15.12	16.89	15.69
2	25.89	26.89	27.14	28.16	27.49	25.46	26.82	27.83
3	36.57	37.80	38.10	37.89	38.42	35.98	34.75	35.66
4	49.86	48.29	47.86	46.89	49.86	48.27	47.81	46.88
6	53.67	55.68	56.91	57.48	58.12	57.42	55.89	59.47
8	65.82	66.81	67.82	68.82	69.83	65.94	63.52	65.80
10	73.58	75.98	76.98	77.81	78.10	77.19	74.19	77.58
12	92.25	93.58	94.87	95.85	96.25	95.66	94.86	97.80

Fig-6: In Vitro Drug Release Studies of (F1-F8) Formulations

The drug release studies of all formulations of Doxorubicin Zinc Oxide nanoparticles were

conducted by means of diffusion apparatus for a time period of 8 hrs. From the drug release studies

as depicted in Figure, the results showed that 8th formulation showed maximum drug release rate of 97.80 % within 12 hrs.

Drug Release Kinetics

The release kinetics for all the prepared Zinc Oxide nanoparticles was evaluated to determine the release behaviour of Doxorubicin from the prepared Zinc Oxide nanoparticles. The release data were analyzed with zero-order kinetic, first-

order kinetic, and Korsmeyer–Peppas kinetic models, as well as the Higuchi kinetic model. It was revealed that the release data from Zinc Oxide nanoparticles fit to Higuchi kinetic model with the highest (r) value, while for free Doxorubicin Zinc Oxide nanoparticles, the release data fit the zero order kinetic model.

In Vitro Drug Release Kinetics

Table-4: Drug Release Kinetics of Optimized Formulation

Time (hrs)	%CDR	SQARE T	LOG T	LOG%CDR	ARA	LOG%ARA
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	15.69	1.000	0.000	1.196	84.310	1.926
2	27.83	1.414	0.301	1.445	72.170	1.858
3	35.66	1.732	0.477	1.552	64.340	1.808
4	46.88	2.000	0.602	1.671	53.120	1.725
6	59.47	2.449	0.778	1.774	40.530	1.608
8	65.8	2.828	0.903	1.818	34.200	1.534
10	77.58	3.162	1.000	1.890	22.420	1.351
12	97.8	3.464	1.079	1.990	2.200	0.342

Zero Order Kinetics

First Order Kinetics

Fig-8: First Order Kinetics of Optimized Formulation

Higuchi Model

Fig-9: Higuchi Model of Optimized Formulation

Korsmeyer Peppas

Fig-10: Korsmeyer Peppas of Optimized Formulation

Stability Studies

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the Zinc Oxide

nanoparticles of formulation F-8 after 90 days. Parameters quantified at various time intervals were shown.

Table-: Stability Studies of all Formulations

	Parameters	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-8	25 ^o C/60%RH % Release	97.80	96.86	95.82	94.72	Not less than 85 %
F-8	30 ^o C/75% RH % Release	97.80	96.75	95.67	94.58	Not less than 85 %
F-8	40 ^o C/75% RH % Release	97.80	96.54	95.05	94.27	Not less than 85 %

CONCLUSION

The current study suggested a unique Doxorubicin polymeric Zinc Oxide nanoparticle formulation for regulated release. A drug encapsulation effectiveness of up to 79.68 % has been attained in this study. Doxorubicin polymeric Zinc Oxide nanoparticles containing zinc nitrate and synthetic polymers were created using the sol to gel method, then the particle size was decreased by sonication formulation using polymeric Zinc Oxide nanoparticles performed well in terms of medication content and encapsulation effectiveness. This shows that the formulation procedure was suitable and reproducible in nature, and it provided a good yield. The formulation with the best encapsulation efficiency was (F-8). It was discovered that the percentage of encapsulation efficiency along with the soy lecithin concentration. According to the method described, permeation studies with dialysis membrane were conducted. The in vitro drug release profiles of all the formulations indicated an initial burst effect, followed by a gradual drug release. The formulations demonstrated good drug release from the polymer. These polymeric Zinc Oxide nanoparticles contained more Doxorubicin and released it more quickly.

REFERENCE

1. Singh A, Singh NB, Hussain I, Singh H, Yadav V, Singh SC (2016) Green synthesis of nano zinc oxide and evaluation of its impact on germination and metabolic activity of Solanum Lycopersicum. *J Biotechnol* 233:84–94
2. Singh A, Singh NB, Hussain I, Singh H, Singh SC (2015) Plant-nanoparticle interaction: an approach to improve agricultural practices and plant productivity. *Int J Pharm Sci Invent* 4(8):25–40.
3. Hussain I, Singh NB, Singh A, Singh H, Singh SC (2016) Green synthesis of nanoparticles and its potential application. *Biotechnol Lett* 38(4):545–560
4. Alves, M. J., Grenho, L., Lopes, C., Borges, J., Vaz, F., Vaz, I. P., et al. (2018). Antibacterial Effect and Biocompatibility of a Novel Nanostructured Zinc Oxide-Coated Gutta-Percha Cone for Improved Endodontic Treatment. *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 92, 840–848. doi:10.1016/j.msec.2018.07.045
5. Andrade, V., Martínez, A., Rojas, N., Bello-Toledo, H., Flores, P., Sánchez-Sanhueza, G., et al. (2018). *J. Prosthet. Dent.* 119, 862–e1. doi:10.1016/j.prosdent.2017.09.015
6. Jowkar, Z., Hamidi, S. A., Shafiei, F., and Ghahramani, Y. (2020). The Effect of Silver, Zinc Oxide, and Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles Used as Final Irrigation Solutions on the Fracture Resistance of Root-Filled Teeth. *Ccide Vol.* 12, 141–148. doi:10.2147/ccide.s253251
7. Moradpoor, H., Safaei, M., Mozaffari, H. R., Sharifi, R., Imani, M. M., Golshah, A., et al. (2021). An Overview of Recent Progress in Dental Applications of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles. *RSC Adv.* 11 (34), 21189–21206. Doi: 10.1039/d0ra10789a.
8. Ramazanzadeh, B., Jahanbin, A., Yaghoubi, M., Shahtahmassbi, N., Ghazvini, K., Shakeri, M., et al. (2015). Comparison of Antibacterial Effects of Zinc Oxide and CuO Nanoparticles Coated Brackets against Streptococcus Mutans. *J. Dent. (Shiraz)* 16 (3), 200–205.
9. Tahmasbi, S., Mohamadian, F., Hosseini, S., and Eftekhari, L. (2019). A Review on the Applications of Nanotechnology in Orthodontics. *Nanomedicine J.* 6 (1), 11–18.
10. Manthe, R. L., Foy, S. P., Krishnamurthy, N., Sharma, B., and Labhassetwar, V. (2010). Tumor Ablation and Nanotechnology. *Mol. Pharm.* 7, 1880–1898. Doi: 10.1021/mp1001944.
11. Jatania, A., and Shivalinga, B. M. (2014). An In Vitro Study to Evaluate the Effects of Addition of Zinc Oxide to an Orthodontic

- Bonding Agent. *Eur. J. Dent.* 08 (01), 112–117. doi:10.4103/1305-7456.126262
12. Gu, M., Hao, L., Wang, Y., Li, X., Chen, Y., Li, W., et al. (2020). The Selective Heavy Metal Ions Adsorption of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles from Dental Wastewater. *Chem. Phys.* 534, 110750. doi:10.1016/j.chemphys.2020.110750.
 13. Wu JM. Heterojunction nanowires of Ag_xZn_{1-x}O–Zinc Oxide photocatalytic and antibacterial activities under visible-light and dark conditions. *J. Phys. Chem. C.* 2015; 119(3):1433–1441.
 14. Tariq Jan JI, Ismail M, Zakaullah M, Naqvi SH, Badshah N. Sn doping induced enhancement in the activity of Zinc Oxide nanostructures against antibiotic resistant *S. aureus* bacteria. *Int. J. Nanomed.* 2013; 8(1):3679–3687.
 15. Schwartz VB, Thétiot F, Ritz S, Pütz S, Choritz L, Lappas A, Förch R, Landfester K, Jonas U. Antibacterial surface coatings from zinc oxide nanoparticles embedded in poly (n-isopropylacrylamide) hydrogel surface layers. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2012; 22(11): 2376–2386.

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